

UNDERSTANDING INVESTOR MOTIVATION AND ATTITUDES TOWARDS POST OFFICE SAVINGS SCHEMES, COIMBATORE

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ABSTRACT

This paper attempts to analyse the investor's behaviour towards post office saving schemes. Indian Post Office Savings Bank being the largest savings institutions in the country play a vital role in mobilizing savings especially in the rural part of the country and offer numerous benefits to the investors. Post Office Savings Schemes are backed by the Government of India, ensuring high security and reliability. They offer multiple options like Recurring Deposits (RD), Fixed Deposits (FD), Public Provident Fund (PPF), and Senior Citizen Savings Scheme (SCSS). With small deposit requirements, these schemes promote savings habits among all income groups. This attempt is made to find the attitude of their accessibility, awareness, and impact on financial inclusion among the population. Despite offering secure and government-backed savings options with attractive interest rates, many individuals, especially in rural and semi-urban areas, lack awareness about the variety of schemes available and their benefits. In this paper we found Majority of the respondents are between the age group of 18-25, Majority of the respondents are Male, Majority of the respondents are qualified undergraduate, Majority of the respondents are self-employed, Majority of the respondent's Income is between 2,00,000-3,00,000.

1. INTRODUCTION

Post Office Savings Schemes have played a crucial role in promoting the habit of saving among both rural and urban populations in India. These schemes, backed by the Government of India, offer secure and attractive investment options to individuals across different income groups. With a variety of schemes such as Savings Accounts, Recurring Deposits, Fixed Deposits, Monthly Income Schemes, and Public Provident Funds, they cater to the diverse financial needs of investors.

Investors choose savings schemes based on their financial goals, risk appetite, and tax-saving benefits. In particular, the Indian Post Office Savings Bank is one of the largest savings institutions in the country, mobilizing funds and contributing to financial inclusion. Studies

suggest that Savings Accounts, Recurring Deposits, and Monthly Income Schemes are among the most preferred choices.

One of the most well-known and easily accessible savings accounts in India is Post Office Savings Account. Both the minimum and the maximum balance that may be kept is Rs.500. A person can open only one account as a single account. The maximum amount that can be placed into a post office savings account is unlimited. People believe in the post offices more than the banks. The post office branches are situated in proximity to their homes. The procedures for opening account in post office is less cumbersome than that of banks.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Dr.G.Prahlad Chowdri ¹ The paper aims to explore investor perceptions of post office savings schemes, especially in areas where formal banking services are limited. It seeks to understand why investor interest in these schemes has declined over time. Post Office Savings Schemes have historically been a reliable investment option, offering security and competitive interest rates. However, changing economic conditions, the rise of private banking institutions, and increased awareness of alternative investment options like mutual funds and stocks may have led to declining interest. The study's objective is relevant, as it provides insights into financial inclusion and the role of postal savings in rural and semi-urban areas.

Harishkumar M ,Dr. Vijay Kumar A B, ² The study effectively analyses investor awareness and perception of Post Office Savings Schemes in Bangalore. It highlights that despite modern investment options, investors still prefer post office savings, with Savings Accounts and Recurring Deposits being the most popular. The findings indicate that gender, age, income, and area of residence significantly influence awareness, while education has no impact. Perceptions about accessibility, long-term benefits, and customization vary based on demographics. However, risk-free savings and account opening methods remain unaffected by these factors. The methodology, using statistical tools like chi-square tests and ANOVA, strengthens the study's reliability. Overall, the research provides valuable insights into investor behaviour, emphasizing the need for increased awareness initiatives.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This paper intends to explore investor's perception towards various post office small saving schemes in areas where the access to formal banking is comparatively low and to find the reasons for decline in investors' interest in these schemes.

1. To determine the investors awareness about Post office savings in Coimbatore City.
2. To identify the most preferred post office savings schemes among investors in Coimbatore city.
3. To analyse the key factors influencing investment decisions in post office savings schemes among Coimbatore city investors.

4. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The present study is aimed at analysing the investor awareness and perception towards the post office savings schemes. In this regard, the investors having account in post office have been selected as the sample respondent and the data collected towards the schemes preferred, awareness of schemes and perception towards the post office savings schemes have been analysed.

5. METHODOLOGY

The data for the study on Post Office saving schemes is collected using both primary and secondary sources. Primary data is gathered through surveys, questionnaires, and interviews with investors, post office staff, and financial experts to understand investor preferences, awareness levels, and satisfaction with the schemes. Secondary data is obtained from government reports, official websites, financial journals, and research articles, which provide information about the features, interest rates, and historical performance of various Post Office saving schemes like PPF, NSC, and RD.

6. SAMPLE SIZE AND POPULATION:

Convenient random sampling method is used and 105 respondents were interviewed.

7. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The Post Office Savings Schemes offer a range of investment options catering to different financial needs. The Post Office Savings Account is a basic deposit scheme offering 4% interest per annum, providing easy liquidity and accessibility. For those looking for regular savings, the Recurring Deposit (RD) offers 6.7% interest, with a tenure of 5 years, making it ideal for disciplined savings. The Time Deposit (TD) provides fixed returns ranging from 6.9% to 7.5%, depending on the tenure (1 to 5 years), with tax benefits available for a 5-year deposit. The Monthly Income Scheme (MIS), offering 7.4% interest, is designed for investors seeking regular income, making it popular among retirees. Long-term investors can opt for the Public Provident Fund (PPF), which provides 7.1% interest, tax-free returns, and a 15-year lock-in period with partial withdrawal options. The National Savings Certificate (NSC) is another tax-saving scheme, offering 7.7% interest with a 5-year maturity period. The Kisan Vikas Patra (KVP) is aimed at those seeking guaranteed returns, doubling the investment in 115 months at an interest rate.

7.1 TOP POST OFFICE INVESTMENT SCHEMES PREFERRED BY COIMBATORE CITY INVESTORS (RANK)

Table 1: POSS PREFERRED BY COIMBATORE CITY INVESTORS

INVESTMENT SCHEMES	Rank
Savings account	II
Recurring deposit	I
Time deposit	IV
Monthly Income Scheme	III
National Saving Scheme	V
Public Provident Fund	VI
Senior Citizen Saving Scheme	VIII
Sukanya Samriddhi Accounts	VII

Source: Primary data

The ranking of Post Office Investment Schemes reflects investor preferences based on security, returns, and accessibility. Recurring Deposit (Rank I) is the most preferred due to their disciplined savings approach and steady returns. Savings Account (Rank II) is highly valued for their liquidity and ease of transactions. The Monthly Income Scheme (Rank III) ranks well, particularly among retirees seeking regular payouts. Time Deposits (Rank IV) appeal to those looking for fixed returns over different tenures. The National Savings Certificate (Rank V) offers tax benefits but ranks lower due to its fixed tenure. Public Provident Fund (Rank VI), despite its tax-free returns, has limited preference due to its long lock-in period. Sukanya Samriddhi Accounts (Rank VII) are less preferred as they cater to a specific demographic group. Senior Citizen Savings Scheme (Rank VIII), while offering high interest, is limited to older investors, leading to lower overall preference.

7.2 TOP FACTORS INFLUENCING INVESTMENT IN POST OFFICE SAVINGS SCHEMES (RANK)

Table 2: Factors Influencing Investment in POSS scheme

Factors Influencing Investment	Rank
Safe and Security	I
Attractive Interest Rates	VII
Tax Benefits	V
Accessibility & Convenience	VI
Flexible Investment Options	III
Loan & Withdrawal Flexibility	VIII
Regular Income Option	IV
Perceived Trust & Awareness	II

Source: Primary data

Safety and security is the first influencing factor, as investors prioritize security above all, as these schemes are government-backed, ensuring low risk and guaranteed returns. Overall, the

ranking suggest that investors prioritize safety, trust, and flexibility over returns and digital convenience, reinforcing the appeal of Post Office Savings Schemes for risk-averse individuals.

Table 3: Preference of schemes of POSS scheme

Preference	Percentage
Post Office Saving Account	29
Time Deposit	22
Recurring Deposit	20
Monthly Income Scheme	8
National Saving Scheme	7
Public Provident Fund	6
Senior Citizen Saving Scheme	5
Sukanya Samridhhi Accounts	3
Total	100

Source: Primary data

The Post Office Savings Account (29%) is the most preferred, likely due to its easy accessibility, liquidity, and security. Time Deposit (22%) and Recurring Deposit (20%) also hold significant preference, reflecting investors' inclination toward stable, fixed-return options. The data suggests that investors prioritize liquidity, safety, and fixed returns over long-term growth and tax benefits. Traditional savings instruments like savings account and fixed deposit dominate due to their familiarity and reliability.

8. FINDINGS AND SUGGESTION

Male investors and the investors in the age group of **30 to 40** years have more awareness towards post office savings schemes. The investors with **UG level educational qualification** possessed the highest awareness. Coimbatore city investors with an income of **Rs.20,000 to Rs.30,000** displayed the highest awareness. The awareness of investors about post office savings scheme was influenced by **Gender, Age, Area of residence and Monthly income** of the investors while educational qualification of the investors have impact on the awareness of investors towards post office savings schemes. Among the various savings schemes offered by post offices, the **recurring account and savings deposit remained** to be the most preferred savings according to the investors in Coimbatore. The perception of investors towards investment process varied in accordance with age, area of residence and monthly income. Area of residence has made significant difference among the investors towards the perception on easy access. The perception of investors towards **long term benefits** and customized products was influenced significantly by gender and area of the residence. The demographic factors have made no significant influence on the perception of investors towards risk free savings and ways of opening savings account. It is found that the perception of the investors has been influenced by area of residence and savings schemes preferred.

9. CONCLUSION

Consumer satisfaction with the Post Office Savings Scheme is generally positive, driven by several key factors. A major reason for this is the security and trust associated with these government-backed schemes, ensuring a sense of financial stability for consumers. Additionally, the widespread presence of Post Office branches in both urban and rural areas enhance accessibility, allowing individuals, including those in remote locations, to easily participate. The competitive interest rates, coupled with diverse options such as the Post Office Savings Account, Monthly Income Scheme, and Public Provident Fund, further contribute to customer satisfaction. Furthermore, the convenience of fund transfers and withdrawals adds to the appeal of these savings options. However, some consumers have raised concerns regarding the limited availability of modern digital services, including efficient online access, as well as the relatively slower processing times compared to private banks. Despite these challenges, overall satisfaction remains high, with most users valuing the reliability, security, and flexibility offered by the Post Office Savings Schemes.

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